

Dynamic postural stability changes of the subjects with toe-in gait due to increase in femoral head anteversion angle during walking

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Abstract

Background: Toe-in gait may be caused by an increase in femoral head anteversion angle. The objective of this study was to assess the impact of toe-in gait on stability during walking.

Method: Two groups were recruited for the study: normal subjects and those with toe-in gait (resulting from an increase in femoral head anteversion angle). Spatiotemporal gait parameters and center of mass (COM) motion were used to evaluate dynamic postural stability.

Results: The mean stride length for normal subjects was 1.1 ± 0.141 meters, compared to 0.943 ± 0.185 meters for those with toe-in gait (p -value=0.01). There was no significant difference in walking speed between the two groups (p -value= 0.3). The motion of the COM in the

vertical (p -value= 0.02) and mediolateral (p -value= 0.01) directions was significantly less in the toe-in gait group compared to normal subjects.

Conclusion: The findings of this study suggest that individuals with toe-in gait exhibit greater stability while walking compared to normal subjects.

Take-Home Message: This study reveals that individuals with a toe-in gait, due to increased femoral head anteversion, show greater postural stability while walking, as indicated by less vertical and mediolateral COM motion. Despite shorter stride lengths, their walking speed remains similar to that of normal subjects. These findings can assist clinicians in understanding and leveraging the stability benefits of toe-in gait during gait assessments and treatment planning.

Keywords: Dynamic stability; toe-in gait; orthopedics; rehabilitation; walking.

INTRODUCTION

Postural stability refers to the interplay between sensory data and motor responses required to maintain a specific posture or transition from one posture to another [1]. Simply producing and exerting force to stabilize the body position in space is insufficient in achieving stability [1,2]. Instead, it is crucial to comprehend when and how to apply corrective forces, ensuring that the central nervous system accurately perceives the body's position in space and whether it is fixed or mobile [3]. To accomplish this, the afferent nerves of the peripheral nervous system gather and organize sensory information from receptors throughout the musculoskeletal system of the body [4]. This information is then integrated within the central nervous system alongside vestibular and visual input, ultimately facilitating motor control [2,4].

It is clear that any issues with these systems can affect standing stability and increase the risk of falls. Musculoskeletal disorders can also impact stability and increase the risk of falls while standing and walking [5]. One deformity that can affect stability is toe-in gait, where a person walks with their feet turned medially instead of pointing straight ahead. Metatarsus adductus, tibia torsion, and femoral head anteversion are the main reasons cited for toe-in gait [6]. At 5 years old, it is hypothesized that this inclination is 26 degrees, at 9 years old it is 21 degrees, and at 16 years old it is 16 degrees. Any elevation in this inclination would be classified as femoral anteversion. An increase in the femoral anteversion angle (the angle between the femoral neck and the axis of the knees) is a contributing factor to toe-in gait (an increase in this angle is known as femoral anteversion). Diagnosis of excessive femoral anteversion involves identifying an enlarged projection of the femoral neck on the femoral shaft [6,7]. In a clinical evaluation, a toe in gait may manifest on one side or both sides, typically assessed through the foot progression angle (FPA) [8]. The FPA indicates the angle of the foot axis in relation to the line of forward movement while walking. A positive FPA indicates an out-toe angle, whereas a negative FPA signifies an in-toe angle [9]. There is no significant link between plantar pressure type and lower-limb rotation in normal children. However, a significant correlation has been discovered between FPA and the medial forefoot impulse in children with neuromuscular diseases. This suggests that these children may have different dynamic stability responses during gait [10].

There has been no research in the literature that has evaluated the stability of subjects with toe-in gait while standing and walking. It appears that a change in toe-in angle can affect the base of support during walking, but there is no study in the literature to support this. Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate the stability of subjects with toe-in gait due to an increase in anteversion angle during walking. The main hypothesis of this study was that subjects with toe-in gait are less stable than normal subjects while walking.

METHODS

Study participants

In this cross-sectional study, two groups were recruited: one group consisted of individuals with a normal gait (11 subjects; 7 girls and 4 boys), and the other group consisted of individuals with a toe-in gait (11 subjects; 7 girls and 4 boys). The subjects with a toe-in gait were referred due to an increase in the femoral head anteversion angle. The main criterion for selecting subjects with toe-in gait was that they had an increased femoral head anteversion angle and did not have any other musculoskeletal disorders that would affect their standing and walking abilities [11]. The diagnosis was made by an orthopedic surgeon using CT scan images of the hip joint. The normal subjects were matched with the toe-in gait subjects based on age and height. The characteristics of the subjects who participated in this study are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. The characteristics of the subjects participated in this study.

Groups	Age (year)	Mass (Kg)	Height (m)	In-R (degree)	In-L (degree)	Ant-R (degree)	Ant-L (degree)
Normal	11.5±1.45	40±4.5	1.52±0.14	----	----	----	----
Toe in gait	11.4±1.7	39.5±3.7	1.5±0.13	131.63±5.66	131.45±5.64	46.84±12.9	50.26±13.14

Note: In-R= Inclination angle in right side, In-L= Inclination angle in left side, Ant-R= Anteversion angle in right side, Ant-L= Anteversion angle in left side

Study protocol

All children participated underwent a standardized assessment procedure in the Biomechanics and Motion Analysis Laboratory. A motion analysis system with 7 high-speed cameras (Qualysis, motion analysis system, Switzerland) was utilized. The data were collected at a frequency of 120 Hz. Participants were instructed to walk at a comfortable speed and complete 5 successful trials. The collected data were filtered with a cut-off frequency of 10 Hz. The center of pressure (COM) data was also collected by force plate (9260AA6 with 600×500×50 mm dimensions) during walking.

Reflective markers were placed on various anatomical landmarks, including the first and fifth metatarsal heads on the right and left sides, the heels on both sides, the medial and lateral malleolus, knee joint epicondyles on both sides, the greater trochanters on both sides, the anterior and posterior superior iliac spines, and the acromioclavicular joints on both sides. Additionally, four clusters, each consisting of four markers, were attached to the anterolateral surfaces of the shank and thigh.

Data process

Various parameters, such as spatiotemporal gait parameters and dynamic stability, were assessed in this study. Dynamic stability was evaluated based on the motion of the COM during walking. The COM motion in the anteroposterior, vertical, and mediolateral directions was normalized to the stride length, leg length, and width of the base of support (the distance between the right and left lateral malleolus), respectively.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was conducted utilizing SPSS 20.0 software (IBM Corporation, Armonk, USA). Descriptive metrics, including the mean and standard deviation, were calculated for individual parameters, with normal distribution confirmed through the Shapiro–Wilk assessment. Since the data had normal distribution, independent t-test was used for final analysis (α was 0.05).

Ethical aspects

Ethical approval was obtained from the Shiraz University of Medical Sciences ethical committee, and a consent form was signed by the parents of each subject prior to data collection.

RESULTS

The mean values of spatiotemporal gait parameters for both normal individuals and those with toe-in gait are presented in Table 2. The mean stride length for normal individuals was 1.1 ± 0.141 meters, while for those with toe-in gait it was 0.943 ± 0.185 meters (p-value of differences = 0.015). There was no significant difference in walking speed between the two groups (p-value > 0.05). The mean cadence for normal subjects was 87.14 ± 8.96 steps/min, compared to 96.77 ± 9.10 steps/min for the toe-in gait group (p-value = 0.01).

Table 2. The mean values of spatiotemporal gait parameters.

Parameters	Stride Length (m)	Speed (m/s)	Cadence (steps/min)	Stance
				Percentage
Normal	1.10 ± 0.141	0.80 ± 0.12	87.14 ± 8.96	64.36 ± 3.82
Toe-in gait	0.943 ± 0.185	0.98 ± 0.14	96.77 ± 9.1	63.43 ± 5.4
P-value	0.015	0.35	0.01	0.32

The mean values of dynamic stability parameters for both groups, normalized to stride length in the anteroposterior direction, were 1.09 ± 0.23 for normal individuals and 1.02 ± 0.06 for those with toe-in gait (p-values = 0.18). There was a significant difference in COM movements in the vertical direction for both groups of participants (p-values = 0.025). The excursion of COM in the mediolateral direction for those with toe-in gait was less than that of normal subjects (p-value = 0.01) (Table3).

Table 3. The mean values of stability parameters of the normal and those with toe in gait.

Parameters	COM in mediolateral	COM in anteroposterior	COM in vertical
	(% of base of support)	(% of stride length)	(% of leg length)
Normal	0.76 ± 0.45	1.09 ± 0.23	0.05 ± 0.01
Toe in gait	0.38 ± 0.09	1.02 ± 0.06	0.04 ± 0.01
P-value	0.01	0.18	0.025

DISCUSSION

Various musculoskeletal disorders can affect a person's ability to stand and walk, increasing their risk of falls [12, 13]. One lower limb deformity that can impact both static and dynamic stability is toe-in gait, caused by an increased anteversion angle of the hip joint. This study used the measures of gait and COM parameters to evaluate and compare the effects of toe in gait and normal gait on dynamic postural stability at normal walking speed. The results of this study indicate that individuals with toe-in gait have a similar walking speed to normal subjects, as shown in Table 2. Additionally, there was no significant difference in the percentage of stance phase between the two groups. The findings in Table 2 suggest that individuals with toe-in gait are able to increase their walking speed by increasing their cadence. This adjustment allows them to shorten their stride length and improve their dynamic stability.

In conclusion, individuals with toe-in gait have appropriate dynamic stability by being able to increase their walking speed through an increase in cadence without an increased risk of falling.

The motion of the COM defines greater dynamic stability in this group of subjects, contradicting the hypothesis that toe-in gait decreases dynamic stability. The results of this study confirmed that individuals with toe-in gait are actually

more stable than normal subjects, as shown in Table 3. This could be attributed to their use of a specific strategy to enhance stability while walking, such as increasing walking speed through a higher cadence and decreasing stride length. This strategy appears to be effective in improving dynamic stability [14], suggesting that individuals with toe-in gait, possibly due to an increased femoral head anteversion angle, may have a lower risk of falling compared to normal subjects [15]. These changes may be caused by an altered pattern of weight distribution in these patients. The redistribution of weight in the body follows a specific sequence in the standard walking motion [16]. This sequence starts by transmitting weight through the talus to the calcaneus, then progresses along the outer edge of the foot. It then travels across the metatarsal bone heads towards the medial edge of the foot, and ultimately transfers to the big toe [17, 18].

Previous research suggests that there is a limited correlation between the FPA and the dispersion of pressure on the plantar surface in healthy children. It seems that these children can dynamically adapt their foot loading arrangements to offset the impact of the FPA. However, in children with in toeing gait, these effects are impaired and they rely on compensatory mechanisms to enhance stability [10].

Study limitations

There are some limitations associated with this study. The primary limitation is that dynamic stability was assessed solely based on the motion of the center of mass and spatiotemporal gait parameters. It is recommended that future studies incorporate additional parameters such as approximate entropy and coordination dimension to provide a more comprehensive analysis.

CONCLUSION

The results of this study did not support the hypothesis that individuals with a toe-in gait have less dynamic stability and a higher risk of falling. The movement of the COM while walking in individuals with a toe-in gait was found to be less than that of individuals with a normal gait, without any significant change in walking speeds. Therefore, it can be concluded that individuals with a toe-in gait are actually more stable than those with a normal gait while walking.

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